

PHENOTYPIC CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIBIOGRAM PATTERNS OF CLINICAL ISOLATES FROM OVINE PNEUMONIA IN AND AROUND TIRUPATI

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ABSTRACT

Respiratory infections are the common in all age group of sheep leading to significant economic losses to sheep farmers and Industry. Microbial resistance to the antibiotics is a huge problem in the treatment of infections. In keeping in view this research study was conducted among twenty sheep flocks in and around Tirupati. Nasal discharges were collected from the ailing sheep using sterile swabs and were labeled and pooled as farm wise. The collected samples were inoculated in nutrient broth and BHI broth, incubated at 37°C for 24 Hrs and later growth was observed. On Gram staining revealed, most of them are both gram positive and gram-negative organisms. Further for conformation of isolates, samples were streaked on selective solid agar media like, Mac Conkey agar, Citramide agar, EMB agar, Edwards's medium and Blood agar medium. Colonies observed are mucoid and pink in color (lactose fermenters), few are white colonies. One sample revealed greenish pigmented colonies on Citramide agar, Gram positive sample was streaked on Edwards's medium, mucoid colonies were observed. Isolate having safety pin like appearance was streaked on Blood agar, initially non-hemolytic colonies latter were converted into hemolytic colonies were observed. For conformation of the organisms the biochemical tests were performed. Based on the biochemical profile the isolates were conformed as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Pasteurella hemolytica* and *E. coli*. The antimicrobial patterns were studied by using locally available antibiotics in Disc diffusion method. Concluded that most of the clinical isolates were showed resistance to penicillins and tetracycline. This study helps in selection of drug to implement the control strategies in this area.

KEY WORDS: ovine pneumonia, isolates, biochemical profile, antibiogram pattern, Disc diffusion method.

INTRODUCTION

Among ovine diseases, pneumonia is very common in occurrence. Due to high mortality among lambs or adult animals, it poses huge economic implications for sheep enterprise (Marru et al.2013). Pneumonia a respiratory disease arising by inflammatory response of lung parenchyma usually accompanied with inflammation of bronchioles or with pleura is still a major disease limiting the production of animals in

the tropics (Attoh-Kotoku et al..2018). Poor management and husbandry practices and diseases of varied etiologies are among the leading bottle necks of sheep and goat production (Molla, 2016). Among the wide range of diseases that effect sheep, respiratory diseases are most frequent as air and blood are their main routes of transmission (Tefaye and Mekonnen, 2016). Over crowding coupled with involuntary inhalation of air polluted with a variety of potentially injurious materials is the most